

ISic1343

I.Sicily inscription 1343

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Alex Antoniou,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di

Catania, inventory 266

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [Ε]νθάδε κίτε

2. Ἀγάθη ἐτέων

3. μ'

4. πρὸ ζ' καλαν

5. δῶν Σεπτε

6. βρίων

Apparatus

Korhonen 2004

Translation (en)

Here lies Agathe, of 40 years, 7 days before the Kalends of September.

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492951

EDCS 39101716

PHI 140840

PHI 316254

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. *Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin.

At 14.0523 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)

Korhonen, K. 2004. Le iscrizioni del Museo civico di Catania : storia delle collezioni, cultura epigrafica, edizione. Helsinki. At 172

Boeckh, A., Franz, J., Curtius, E., Kirchhoff, A., Roehl, H. 1828-1887. Corpus Inscriptionum Graecarum. Berlin. At 4.9480

Wessel, C. 1989. Inscriptiones Graecae Christianae Veteres Occidentis. *Inscriptiones Christianae Italiae.* Bari. At 1379

Libertini, G 1930. Il Museo Biscari. Milan. At 318 no.9

Ferrua, A 1989. Note e giunte alle iscrizioni cristiane antiche della Sicilia. Vatican. At no.434

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